

Dielectric Properties of BaTiO_{3-δ}

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DECLARATION

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This is to certify that the thesis entitled “Dielectric properties of $\text{BaTiO}_{3-\delta}$ ” submitted by Ms Monalisa Yadav Registration No. 15MS168 dated 24th June 2020, a student of Department of Physical Sciences of the BS-MS Program of IISER Kolkata, is based upon her own research work under my supervision. This is also to certify that neither the thesis nor any part of it has been submitted for any degree or any other academic award anywhere before. In my opinion, the thesis fulfils the requirement for the award of the degree of Master of Science

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Abstract

Dielectric Properties of $\text{BaTiO}_{3-\delta}$

Barium titanate (BTO) has excellent electrical and optical properties. It is widely used as multilayer ceramic capacitors since it has a very high value of dielectric constant. BTO is a ferroelectric and undergoes many structural phase transitions. By changing the composition of the crystal structure or by doping or through introducing defects, it can be used either as insulators, semiconductors or even as metals. In spite of BTO being one of the most studied ceramics, many questions regarding the conduction mechanism in semiconducting BTO and experimental evidence of persistence of both metallicity and ferroelectricity in oxygen deficient BTO have remained unanswered. In this thesis, we have studied the properties of oxygen deficient Barium Titanate ($\text{BaTiO}_{3-\delta}$). We have studied the effect of oxygen vacancies and the effect of temperature variations on the electrical properties of BTO through Impedance Spectroscopy and have also tried to quantify the change in stoichiometry of pure BTO through Rietveld Refinement.

Contents

Chapter 1 Introduction	7
Chapter 2 Background and Overview	8
2.1 Barium Titanate (BaTiO ₃).....	8
2.1.1 Crystal Structure.....	8
2.1.2 Phase Transition of BaTiO ₃	10
2.1.3 Synthesis of BaTiO ₃ powder.....	12
2.1.4 Synthesis of BaTiO ₃ pellet.....	14
2.2 X-ray diffraction studies (XRD) and Rietveld Refinement of BaTiO ₃	16
2.3 Dielectric Properties	21
2.4 Ferroelectrics	23
2.5 Electrical properties of oxygen deficient BaTiO ₃	24
Chapter 3 Objectives	27
Chapter 4 Experimental Techniques	28
4.1 Impedance Spectroscopy.....	28
4.2 Temperature dependent Impedance Spectroscopy	36
Chapter 5 Results	39
5.1 Sample preparation of BaTiO ₃ pellet.....	39
5.2 Sample preparation of oxygen deficient BaTiO ₃ powder and pellet.....	40
5.3 X-ray diffraction and Rietveld Refinement of pristine and oxygen deficient BaTiO ₃ ..	42
5.4 Temperature dependent Impedance Spectroscopy	46
5.4.1 Contact Optimization for BaTiO ₃ pellet.....	47
5.4.2 Dielectric Study of oxygen deficient BTO annealed at 900°C	48
Chapter 6 Conclusion.....	55
References	56

Chapter 1 Introduction

BaTiO₃ (BTO) has been a widely studied ceramic due to its early discovery in the 1940's and its simple crystal structure belonging to the perovskite family. BTO finds applications in numerous technological fields as a ferroelectric, dielectric, piezoelectric, pyroelectric and as a semiconductor. Besides its tremendous applications in industries, it shows interesting physics which includes the various structural phase transitions and the corresponding variations in electrical properties, the mechanism of conduction, the type of ferroelectricity etc. Many questions have been answered in the past, but still a few questions remain a topic of investigation.

Till now it is not very clear, which mechanism is responsible for the conduction in oxygen deficient or electron doped BTO whether it is polaronic type or conduction band type? Recently, metal-insulator transition has been observed in oxygen deficient or electrostatic doped BTO and some papers have claimed the persistence of both ferroelectricity and metallicity in BTO. But the exact physics has still not been found that can support two contradictory mechanisms of localisation of polarised charges (ferroelectricity) and simultaneously the presence of itinerant electrons that are responsible for the metallic behaviour of Oxygen deficient BTO.

In this thesis, we have studied the temperature dependent dielectric behaviour of both pristine and oxygen deficient BTO. We have tried to optimize the annealing conditions and also tried to quantify the deficiency of oxygen in BTO through Rietveld technique.

This work is primarily experimental except the theoretical calculations in determining the quantity of oxygen deficiency through Rietveld Refinement. All theoretical results have been compared against experimental data whenever available.

This brief introduction is followed by chapter 2 on literature review of BTO, the method of synthesis, X-ray diffraction, the Rietveld technique and the dielectric, ferroelectric, semiconducting and metallic properties. Chapter 3 discusses about the objectives of the thesis and the motivation behind the problem studied. Chapter 4 talks about all the experimental techniques used in this thesis. All results from sample preparation, to characterization, to temperature dependent Impedance Spectroscopy has been mentioned in chapter 5. Finally in chapter 6, conclusions have been summarized and future outlook has been mentioned.

Chapter 2 Background and Overview

2.1 Barium Titanate (BaTiO₃)

Barium Titanate (BaTiO₃) is a ceramic belonging to the ABX₃ (A and B are cations and X is an anion bonded to both the cations) perovskite family. It is the first ferroelectric ceramic discovered by Wainer and Salomon in 1942 [1]. The material has interesting physics and undergoes numerous structural phase transitions. Above 120°C, BaTiO₃ is stable in cubic structure. On lowering down the temperature below 120°C, it undergoes a transition from paraelectric cubic to ferroelectric tetragonal structure. On further lowering down the temperature, at 5°C, it transits to orthorhombic structure and below -90°C it is stable in the rhombohedral structure. Both the low temperature phases are ferroelectric in nature. BaTiO₃ also has a high temperature transition to hexagonal structure at 1460°C [2]. BaTiO₃ finds tremendous applications because it can be easily prepared, is chemically and mechanically very stable [3] and has excellent ferroelectric, dielectric, piezoelectric and pyroelectric properties. The method employed for preparation of the material has significant effect on the properties of the materials. The Curie temperature also fluctuates between 120°C to 130°C depending on the method used to make the material. The powder is mainly synthesized through traditional solid state method, various chemical methods and mechanochemical method discussed further in details in section 2.1.3. BaTiO₃ (BTO) has high dielectric constant greater than 1000 and low dielectric loss [4]. Therefore, it is highly used as capacitors and in multilayer capacitors. Doped BaTiO₃ is also used as semiconductors, positive thermal Coefficient (PTC) resistors [5]. BTO based ferroelectrics have high polarization, large permittivity and large strain which makes them excellent materials for use in piezoelectric transducers [6]. What makes BTO even more attractive for industrial applications is that, it is lead free and hence environment friendly [7].

2.1.1 Crystal Structure

BTO has a perovskite structure with a general formula of ABX₃, where A and B are metallic ions and X is a non-metallic ion. X can be F¹⁻, Cl¹⁻, O²⁻ but mostly it is the oxide anion. A is usually bigger than the B cation. A ions are monovalent, divalent or trivalent for example Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Y³⁺ and B ions are pentavalent, tetravalent or trivalent respectively. The smaller cations are mostly Nb⁵⁺, Sn⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺, Ti⁴⁺, Mn⁴⁺, In³⁺, and Ga³⁺. The undistorted, ideal perovskite structure is cubic in form with the B ion occupying the centre of the cube, the

A ions at the cube corners with the X anions at the centre of each face of the cube (figure 1a). The coordination number of A is 12 and that of B is 6. The structure can also be described as AX_6 octahedron with B ion occupying the void of 8 such octahedra as shown in figure 1b. In case of $BaTiO_3$, the Ba ions are large in size and the void formed by the BaO_6 octahedra is too large as compared to the size of Ti ion. This causes the Ti ion to get off-centred towards the oxygen ions due to random thermal motion. When an electric field is applied, Ti gets aligned to the field direction from a random orientation and because valency of Ti ion is 4+, this causes large polarization and high dielectric constant. The interaction between the dipole moment leads to the formation of ferroelectric domains [8].

But the ideal structure is not very common and most of the perovskites found have a distorted structure with a reduced symmetry. It is this reduced symmetry which gives rise to many electric and magnetic properties that find great applications in industries. The distorted structure can be orthorhombic, rhombohedral, monoclinic, tetragonal or triclinic [9].

The distortion in the ideal structure is mainly caused by size effects, deviation from the ideal composition and the Jahn- Teller effect [10]. Many a times more than a single factor contributes to the distortion.

In the cubic structure, the lattice parameter a can be written in the form of equation 1,

$$a = (r_A + r_X)^{0.5} = 2 (r_A + r_X) \quad (1)$$

The equation can be rearranged to be written in the form of equation 2,

$$t = \frac{(r_A + r_X)}{(r_B + r_X)^{0.5}} \quad (2)$$

where t is defined as the Goldschmidt's tolerance factor. Deviation of t from ideal value of 1 gives rise to different crystal structures. But the size effect cannot be regarded as an exact description of the distortion since the perovskites are not purely ionic compounds and the t value depend on the value of ionic radius taken.

Sometimes the B ions in ABX_3 are Jahn-Teller active ions, for example in $LaMnO_3$, the d orbitals of Mn ion undergo splitting into 3 t_g and 1 e_g levels which causes an elongation of the MnO_6 octahedron.

Oxygen vacancies in ABO_3 structures can also cause distortion of structure. These kind of perovskites are called defect perovskites.

Figure 1: ABO_3 structure. A) A ions are shown blue in colour sitting at the cube corners, B ion in red at the centre and X ions in green at the centre of each face of the cube. B) The perovskite structure can also be described in the octahedron shown in red shapes[11].

2.1.2 Phase Transition of $BaTiO_3$

BTO undergoes several structural phase transitions from low temperature to -90°C to high temperature 1460°C . The most widely studied transition is from paraelectric cubic to ferroelectric tetragonal structure at 120°C . BTO is ferroelectric in all the phases below 120°C . At 0°C it undergoes a transition from tetragonal to orthorhombic and to rhombohedral phase at -90°C . The various phases of BTO have been showed in figure 2. BTO also undergoes a phase transition at a very high temperature of 1460°C to paraelectric hexagonal structure. The presence of ferroelectricity in lower symmetries of BTO is due to off-centred Ti ion in the oxygen octahedra which breaks the space symmetry and gives rise to spontaneous polarization.

Figure 2: Unit cells of BaTiO₃. a) Symmetric cubic phase b) Tetragonal phase with the polarization axis parallel to the c axis caused by lengthening of the cell in this direction c) orthorhombic phase with the polarization along the surface diagonal and c) rhombohedral phase with the polarization axis parallel to the body diagonal.

In the paraelectric, centrosymmetric cubic phase, BTO obeys the Curie Weiss law given by the formula in equation 3

$$\varepsilon = \frac{C}{T - T_c} \quad (3)$$

Where ε is the dielectric constant, C is a material specific Curie Constant, T is the absolute temperature and T_c is the Curie temperature both given in Kelvin.

All the phase transitions along with their dielectric constant values and transition temperatures have been shown in figure 3. Since the phase transition is of first order type, properties like dielectric constant and lattice parameters show discontinuities at the transition temperatures. The dielectric constant shows a spike at the Curie temperature below which it decreases with temperature. A few more peaks are observed at lower temperatures corresponding to the various low temperature phase transitions but their values are much smaller than that of dielectric constant at the Curie temperature. The transition temperatures

also differ based on the structure, size, defects, impurities and the method of synthesis. Irrespective of the variations of the transition temperature, the thermal hysteresis occurring at 0°C and -90°C remains the same.

Figure 3 : The dielectric constant versus the temperature graph has been shown. The various jumps correspond to the phase transitions. Ba, O, Ti ions have been shown in green, red and blue respectively. The blue arrow points towards the direction of polarization (P_s). The double lines at the transition temperature clearly depict the thermal hysteresis effect.

2.1.3 Synthesis of BaTiO₃ powder

In the past years numerous methods have been developed to synthesis BaTiO₃ powders. The properties of the material produced depend largely on the synthesis route. Few of the common methods used for synthesis of powder have been mentioned below.

2.1.3.1 Conventional solid state reaction

This method involves ball milling of BaCO₃ or BaO and TiO₂ powders. The mixture which is obtained is calcined at high temperature ranging from 800°C to 1200°C and sometimes even higher than 1300°C [12-15]. But the quality of the powder produced by this method is poor. The size of the particle is too large, various agglomerates are formed, and also results in the formation of impurity phases which ultimately results in poor electrical behaviour of the material [16].

To avoid these problems, a number of chemical methods have been employed to produce BaTiO₃ powder which results in formation of single phase, homogenous and finer powder of submicron size.

2.1.3.2 Chemical Methods

Good Quality BaTiO₃ powders can be synthesised from a number of chemical routes such as Hydrothermal, coprecipitation, polymeric precursor and sol-gel method.

- Polymeric precursor synthesis- In this method a solution of metal-ions, citric acid and ethylene glycol is polymerized to form a polyester type resin. The advantage of this method is that the metal ion is frozen in the network and during final heating stage no segregation of cations takes place [18].
- Coprecipitation method- Ions are mixed at the molecular level under controlled conditions which results in highly homogenous particles. It is a very simple, convenient and widely used technique [13-14, 17].
- Sol-Gel Synthesis- In this method metal alkoxide is partially hydrolysed to form reactive monomers followed by polycondensation of monomers to form sol which is again hydrolysed to begin polymerization and cross-linking leading to the formation of a gel. An amorphous oxide is formed on drying the gel which is in the end thermally treated so that crystallization can take place [5].
- Hydrothermal Synthesis- The BaTiO₃ powder produced by this method have very fine particle size and the variation in the sizes are also less which helps in sintering and formation of good thin dielectric layers. This method involves forced hydrolysis of reagents at extremely high pressure and moderate temperature less than 200°C. This method is very easy and no undesirable products are formed. This method is comparatively cheaper as it does not require elaborate apparatus and expensive reagents [16].

Disadvantages of the chemical methods- Even though the particles formed from the chemical routes are finer in size, homogenous and phase pure, they are not so suitable for the production at the industrial scale. Sol-gel method requires a very high temperature. Stoichiometric deviations are produced in the powder produced by coprecipitation and hydrothermal method. Polymeric precursor method consumes a lot of time and requires large

amount of organic materials. It is due to these disadvantages that Mechanochemical synthesis is normally used for production of BaTiO₃ powder at the industrial level [5].

2.1.3.3 Mechanochemical Synthesis

This method is beneficial to produce nano-sized oxides and superconductors by mechanically treating the ceramic powders [19]. Mechanical action leads to formation of stress fields in solids during the milling process. During milling, heat is released, new surfaces and different crystal lattice defects are formed which initiates the solid-state reaction [20-22]. In order to get the desired material properties, it is essential to understand the accumulated deformation energy produced by the action of mechanical stress which helps in understanding the microstructure of the powder. This method is useful for industrial applications.

2.1.4 Synthesis of BaTiO₃ pellet

Theoretically, the stability of the ceramic compounds depends on ionic and covalent bonds present in them. But in general the knowledge of these bonds are not enough to understand the stability of the materials because many of the times there are defects present in the microstructure which plays an important role in determining the properties of the materials. These defects are usually formed during processing of the materials but, by controlling the parameters and conditions, we can control the final shape of the compounds including its microstructure.

The processing of ceramics requires three basic steps which are powder manufacture (discussed in section 2.1.3), then consolidation of the powder into compact shapes and finally firing which eliminates the impurities, void spaces and helps in developing the microstructure of the ceramic [23]. Each step has the ability to develop a heterogeneity which can either remain in the final product or can develop other defects during the pelletization and sintering processes.

Before pelletization the powder must have the desired properties for example it should be pure otherwise it can cause difference in stoichiometry. The powder should be homogenous, should have smaller size particles. The sintering temperature can be considerably lowered by reducing the particle size because rate of densification during pelletization and sintering is inversely proportional to the size of the particle. The particles should have a spherical shapes, high packing density and the particles should have less variability in the sizes which otherwise can promote undesirable grain growth and lead to inhomogeneous microstructure.

After the grinding, crushing and addition of binders to the powder, agglomerates are formed. Agglomerates mostly consist of particles bonded by forces like electrostatic or Vander Waal forces. Besides these, the agglomerates have a number of interconnected pores. These agglomerates play a very important role in affecting the sintering and pelletization process and ultimately in determining the strength of the pellets. The agglomerates determine the particle packing, distribution of the void and the microstructure of the green compacts (the pellet prior to sintering).

The green compacts have been formed by the process of uniaxial die pressing. In this process, powder is placed in die and pressure is applied to get the desired compaction. Usually a lubricant (mostly organic material) is used in between the powder and die which weakens the friction, help in pressing and removing the pellet and preventing die abrasion. Lubricants also help in producing homogenous green compact by reducing the density variation among the particles of the pellet. Binder added to the powder during the crushing and grinding process also provides lubrication between the powder particles and helps in forming temporary bonds between them. Therefore the quantity and the properties of the binder like the solubility, strength, deformability and its evaporation temperature (the lower the better) should be taken into account while choosing the binder.

Binder is usually mixed with water and heated to form viscous glue. The amount of water is high because it helps in lowering the glass transition temperature (defined as the temperature where the amorphous solid undergoes a transition from hard, brittle state to viscous, rubbery state [24]) of binder. The greater is the proportion of water as compared to the binder greater is the density of green compacts. If the powder has very fine sized particles, they do not have the free flowing properties which are required during pressing of powder into green compacts in a die; binder helps in bonding the fine particles into agglomerates which do have the desired free flowing properties.

Compaction of powder into pellet usually comprises of four processes. First one is the filling of void in between the agglomerates followed by plastic deformation of agglomerates. Thirdly, the filling of void in between the particles of agglomerate and lastly the plastic deformation of the particles that make up the agglomerates. A density variation is formed in the pellet due to the frictional forces present between the wall and the powder and the pressure felt by the powder is much lower than the actual pressure applied in the uniaxial die.

After making green compact, it is usually sintered to make pellets with a higher density and greater strength.

Sintering is a process where the powder particles fuse together to produce a dense end product. It is usually done by heating the green compact at a suitable temperature called the sintering temperature. The free energy of the final dense sintered pellet is much lower than that of pellet before sintering because fusion of particles causes the surface area to decrease and hence lower the free surface energy. The green density of the pellet and also the variation in the green density greatly influence the sintering behaviour and the end microstructure. The bulk density of the pellet increases at a faster rate on increasing the green density. Besides densification, grain growth also occurs during sintering. Sintering the pellet also helps in removal of binder and other organic materials which are present in the pellet either in the form of lubricants used or in the form of impurities. If the binder remains after sintering it can adversely affect the microstructure and produce internal defects in the pellet thereby altering its properties. All these processes lead to the shrinkage of a green compact into final dense pellets.

2.2 X-ray diffraction studies (XRD) and Rietveld Refinement of BaTiO₃

Since years people have studied X-ray diffraction of various materials in order to determine their crystal structure. All the optical, electronic, magnetic, dielectric, ferroelectric properties depend on the atomic arrangement of atoms within the unit cell; therefore the characterization of the material becomes a really important part of any study on materials. Each substance is known to produce a unique diffraction profile. The final XRD profile is a combination of all the substances in the material and each substance in the mixture produces a pattern independent of others. The diffraction profile helps us to get both qualitative and quantitative information about the material.

The constructive interference of the diffracted rays from the planes of the lattice gives rise to the Bragg peaks. The condition for constructive interference is given by Bragg's law (equation 4)

$$2d\sin\theta = n\lambda \quad (4)$$

Where d is the distance between the lattice planes, θ is the angle between the X-ray source and the lattice plane, n is any positive integer and λ is the wavelength of the monochromatic X-ray source. The calculated intensity is given by the formula in equation 5

$$Y_{calc(i)} = s \sum_k L_k |F_{hk}|^2 \phi(2\theta_i - 2\theta_k) P_k A + y_{background(i)} \quad (5)$$

where s is the scale factor, L_k contains the Lorentz, polarization and multiplicity factors, ϕ is the reflection profile function that models both instrumental and sample effects, P_k is the preferred orientation function, A is the absorption function and F_{hkl} is the structure factor given by the formula (equation 6)

$$F_{hkl} = \sum_{n=1}^N f_n \exp(2\pi i(hx + ky + lz)) \quad (6)$$

Where f_n is the atomic structure factor and is a measure of the scattering strength of the atoms, h, k, l are the miller indices of the scattering plane, x, y, z is the position coordinates of the atom n and N is the total number of atoms in the unit cell. From the above equations, we can see that calculated intensity is directly proportional to the square of the structure factor. Therefore the unit cell gives us various information of the crystal structure like the distance between the planes, lattice parameters, the crystallite size, various phases formed and the position of atoms in the unit cell.

In order to understand the crystal structure, numerous methods have been used like the Le Bail method, the Rietveld method etc. Rietveld refinement technique is widely used and is considered to be more accurate. This technique matches the experimental intensity data with that of the structural model given by the user by refining various parameters till a close match is reached. According to the Rietveld method, the model is refined by the least-squares fitting process in equation 7

$$S = \sum_i w_i |y_{obs(i)} - y_{calc(i)}|^2 \quad (7)$$

Where s is the residue or the difference between the calculated intensity and the experimental intensity, the steps are denoted by i , $y_{obs(i)}$ is the observed or the experimental intensity at step i , $y_{calc(i)}$ is the calculated intensity of the model at position i and the weights w_i is given by the formula (equation 8)

$$w_i = \frac{1}{\sigma_{peak(i)}^2 + \sigma_{background(i)}^2} \quad (8)$$

where $\sigma_{peak(i)}$ is the standard deviation of the peak and $\sigma_{background(i)}$ is the standard deviation associated with background intensity.

A number of quantitative and qualitative information can be gathered from the XRD profile and Rietveld refinement. The Rietveld method removes the background noise and corrects for various instrumental errors like zero shift, displacement error and error in the wavelength of the incident wave. The lattice parameters are calculated from the d-spacing by the following formula (equation 9)

$$\frac{1}{d_{hkl}^2} = \frac{1}{V^2} [(hbc)^2 \sin^2 \alpha + (kca)^2 \sin^2 \beta + (lab)^2 \sin^2 \gamma] \quad (9)$$

Where d is the distance between the lattice planes a, b, c are lattice distances in the x, y, z direction respectively and α, β, γ are the angles between x and y, y and z and x and z axis respectively. h, k, l are the miller indices and V is the volume of the unit cell given by the following formula in equation 10

$$V = abc[1 + 2\cos\alpha\cos\beta\cos\gamma - (\cos 2\alpha + \cos 2\beta + \cos 2\gamma)]^{0.5} \quad (10)$$

The Rietveld method allows us to fit the peak shape from a number of options available from the software like the Gaussian, Lorentzian, Pseudo-Voigt, Pearson VII etc, The most widely used function is the Pseudo-Voigt method which uses a combination of both Gaussian and Lorentzian functions. The Pseudo-Voigt pV(x) is given by (equation 11)

$$pV(x) = \eta L(x) + (1 - \eta)G(x) \quad (11)$$

where L(x) is the Cauchy Lorentzian function and G(x) is the Gaussian function and η is the mixing parameter given by (equation 12).

$$\eta = \eta_0 + X2\theta \quad (12)$$

where X is Lorentzian isotropic strain parameter and both X and η_0 are refinable parameters.

Full width at half maxima (FWHM) is given by the following formula in equation 13

$$FWHM^2 = (U \tan 2\theta + V \tan 2\theta + W) + \frac{I_G}{\cos^2 2\theta} \quad (13)$$

where U, V, W are refinable half-width parameters and I_G is the gaussian isotropic size parameter and can be refined. FWHM is helpful in calculating the crystallite size D given by the well-known Debye Scherrer's formula in equation 14

$$D = \frac{0.94\lambda}{FWHM \cos\theta} \quad (14)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the monochromatic X-ray source and θ is peak position.

Using the Rietveld method we can calculate the occupancy (Occu) of the atom in the unit cell given by the following formula in equation 15

$$Occu = \frac{c * m}{M} \quad (15)$$

Where c is the chemical occupancy of the ion in the unit cell, m is the Wyckoff multiplicity of the site and M is the general multiplicity of the space group. Occupation number is not very stable during refinement and should only be refined after having a very stable model for our experimental data.

Rietveld method allows us to correct for the change in intensity caused by atomic displacements of atoms from their ground state position. Thermal motion in a lattice gives rise to vibrations in atoms which can lead to the attenuation of the X-ray wave scattering from the ions. The Debye-Waller factor accounts for this change and can be refined in the form of overall B factor, isotropic and anisotropic B factor. Lower the B value implies more ordered is the atom in the crystal and higher the B value of the ions makes the structure more flexible. Like Occupation number, B value is also very sensitive to refinement and is not very stable, therefore should be refined only after getting a close accurate model for the experimental data.

Non-random orientation of crystallites can arise during crystallization, growth, sample preparation which can cause the grains to prefer certain crystallographic direction. This can cause variation in intensity of the peaks of the spectrum as there are either more or less peaks with certain orientations. To correct for the preferred orientation, Rietveld technique provides us two refinable parameters G1 and G2. The asymmetry parameter act as a multiplier to the peak shape. The asymmetry can be corrected with the help of four refinable parameters P1, P2, P3 and P4 which are all independent from each other. Their starting values should be very

less around 0.01 and should not be kept fixed during refinement as it can lead to bad refinement or divergence[25].

Although the Rietveld method allows for the correction for a number of parameters, one has to be careful while refining the parameters. Refining a large numbers of parameters at the same time can cause a singular matrix. A prior judgement should be made to check which parameters should be kept fixed and which should be allowed to vary. It is better to start the refinement with the parameters that are stable and independent like the scale factor, zero shift, instrumental displacement or incident wave wavelength error, lattice parameters, background points followed by peak shape and preferred orientation parameters. The thermal displacement parameters and occupancy parameters should only be refined after getting a very accurate, reliable and stable model for our data otherwise; refining these parameters can give highly unphysical values. Also the parameters which are correlated should be refined separately like the thermal parameters and occupancy parameters. The overall scale parameter and the occupation numbers are also highly correlated. During the refining process instead of being in the global minima, the model might get trapped in the local minima of the refinable parameter. This can lead to unphysical values of the parameters and wrong matching of the model with the experimental data.

In order to check for the accuracy of our model or how close our model describes the actual experimental data, Rietveld technique provides a number of agreement factors [25] like the profile factor (R_p), weighted profile factor (R_{wp}), expected weighted profile factor (R_{exp}), Bragg factor (R_B), Goodness of fit indicator (S), reduced chi-square (χ^2) and crystallographic R_F -Factor (R_F) given by the following formulae (equations 16-21).

$$R_p = 100 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - y_{ci}|}{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i} \quad (16)$$

Where y_i is the observed intensity at point i and y_{ci} is the calculated intensity at point i and n is the total number of points

$$R_{wp} = 100 \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i |y_i - y_{ci}|^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i y_i^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (17)$$

$$R_{exp} = 100 \left[\frac{n - p}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i y_i^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (18)$$

Where p is the total number of refined parameters

$$S = \frac{R_{wp}}{R_{exp}} \quad (19)$$

$$\chi^2 = S^2 \quad (20)$$

$$R_B = 100 \frac{\sum |I_{obs} - I_{calc}|}{\sum |I_{obs}|} \quad (21)$$

Where I_{obs} and I_{calc} are the integrated observed and integrated calculated intensities respectively.

R_{exp} gives the value of best fitting of the experimental profile that can be possible. A lower R_{exp} is an indicator of a high quality data. R_p and R_{wp} describe how close the theoretical data is to the actual experimental data [26]. According to equation 20 and 21, S and χ^2 should ideally reach a value 1, in case of the best match obtained. Often this is not the case, but during refining we try to get as close to 1 as possible. R_B is useful because its value depends only on the structural parameters and not on the profile parameters.

Although XRD is extremely helpful in understanding the crystal structure of the material, one of its main disadvantages is that it cannot detect smaller atoms with atomic number less than 13 accurately. As X-ray rays interact with the electron cloud of the ions, these smaller ions with less number of electrons almost remain invisible to the rays.

2.3 Dielectric Properties

Dielectrics are those materials that do not conduct electricity on the application of an Electric Field. The field causes shift in the centre of the positive and negative charges in the material, such that the material acquires an electric dipole moment. Dipole moment per unit volume is called the polarization. The polarization is always proportional to the applied electric field given by the following formula in equation 22.

$$\mathbf{P} = \epsilon_0 \chi_e \mathbf{E} \quad (22)$$

Where \mathbf{P} is the polarization, ϵ_0 is the dielectric permittivity (degree of polarization experienced by the dielectric under the influence of Electric field) in vacuum \mathbf{E} is the applied electric field and χ_e is the dielectric susceptibility (measure of the dielectric's ability to form dipoles in response to the electric field) given by the following equation 23

$$\chi_e = \epsilon_r - 1 \quad (23)$$

where ϵ_r is the relative permittivity (ratio of dielectric permittivity in the medium and dielectric permittivity in vacuum. Value of dielectric constant in vacuum is 8.85×10^{-14} Farad/cm). However the molecule in the interior of the dielectric experiences an electric field different from that applied; therefore, the final polarization of the material depends on the local electric field and the polarizability of the molecule.

At the microscopic level, polarization can be of many types given below-

- **Electronic polarization:** This kind of polarization arises in the dielectric medium due to the displacement of the centre of positive charges from negative charges
- **Ionic Polarization:** Materials that have ionic bonds in them, on application of the electric field, the distance between the positive and the negative ion further increases giving rise to a dipole moment.
- **Orientational Polarization:** Some materials have permanent dipole moments but due to thermal motion they remain randomly oriented. On application of an external electric field, they orient in the direction of the field, given rise to a net dipole moment.
- **Spontaneous Polarization:** In ferroelectric materials, dipole moment arises due to shifting of ion from the centre of the unit cell.
- **Space Charge or Interfacial polarization:** This kind of polarization occurs due to accumulation of charges at the interface of two materials or between two regions within the same material or between the electrode and the dielectric medium on the application of an external electric field.

The degree of charge storage in a dielectric medium is measured by its dielectric constant. When an electric field is applied between two metallic plates that have a dielectric medium between them, one of the plates become positively charged and the other becomes negatively charged. Thus the electric field causes polarization in the dielectric medium. Depending on the kind of polarization in the dielectric medium, different materials show variations in the dependence of dielectric constant on temperature. Electronic polarization is almost insensitive to temperature. In ionic polarization, with increase in temperature, number of charge carriers and mobility increases leading to an increase in the polarization value. In orientational polarization since the permanent dipoles are randomly oriented due to thermal motion; they show a greater polarization at low temperatures. Dielectric Constant also

depends on the frequency of the applied electric field. The polarization requires time to respond to the ac field with continuously changing direction. The frequency after which the dipoles cannot respond to the fast changing field is called the relaxation frequency. Electronic polarization can respond to high frequency fields while the rest of the polarization only respond at lower frequencies since molecules do not have enough time to reorient and align parallel to the fast changing fields.

Materials that have low dielectric constant are used as electric insulators and those with high dielectric constant are used as capacitors [28]. Dielectrics do have a limit to which electric field can be applied. High electric field causes the material to break down and conduct electricity which destroys the purpose of the usage of the dielectric material. The maximum field that the material can sustain is called dielectric strength and varies with different materials. Old capacitors, impurities in the dielectric or very strong field can generate electrons in the conduction band which on applying high electric field accelerate very strongly, they can further transfer their high energies to valence electrons, thereby creating large number of conduction electrons which in the long run can cause the dielectric to burn or melt.

A group of dielectrics can be classified as piezoelectric, materials that develop polarization on the application of stress. A sub group of piezoelectrics are pyroelectric materials that have polarization in one crystallographic direction. On the application of heat, the material expands leading to a mechanical deformation which increases the pre-existing polarization. A sub group of pyroelectrics are ferroelectrics which have been discussed in detail in the next section.

2.4 Ferroelectrics

Some materials have spontaneous polarization without an application of an Electric field. The temperature at which these materials lose their spontaneous polarization is called the Curie temperature. Spontaneous polarization can be switched in the opposite direction on the application of a strong electric field. We know that in BTO, the shifting of the Ti ion from the centre of the TiO_6 octahedra causes symmetry breaking and give rise to the dipole moment in the unit cell. Usually the thermal interaction dominates over the exchange interaction between the dipole moments and so we get randomly oriented domains with different polarization directions. But all the dipole moments point in the same direction within each domain. Figure 4 describes the Polarization versus electric field (P-E loop). On increasing the

electric field, the polarization increases as the domains start aligning parallel to the electric field till it reaches a saturation value (P_s) and the polarization does not change further even on increasing the electric field (path O-C). Once we start decreasing the electric field, the polarization starts decreasing as due to thermal motion few domains are able to orient along the electric field direction (path C-D). However even when the electric field is 0, the polarization is not zero as few domains remain oriented in the direction of applied field. This is called remnant polarization (P_r). The value of the field required for the polarization to become 0 is called the coercive field (E_c). On applying the field in the opposite direction causes the domains to switch direction leading to polarization in the opposite direction (path E-F). As we further increase the electric field the polarization also increases till it reaches a saturation value. Thus a hysteresis (dependence of the state of the system on its history) loop can be observed. Therefore at a particular value of the electric field, more than 1 possible value of polarization is possible depending on how the field changed in the past. Above the Curie temperature for tetragonal- cubic phase transition the hysteresis loop disappears.

Figure 4: Polarization versus Electric Field (P-E) loop showing the Saturation polarization (P_s), Remnant polarization (P_r), Coercive field (E_c) [28].

2.5 Electrical properties of oxygen deficient BaTiO₃

Electrical properties of undoped BaTiO₃ (BTO) have been a topic of investigation since years. It is known that stoichiometric BTO loses some amount of oxygen on annealing at high temperature. The amount of oxygen loss depends on a number of factors like annealing

temperature, atmosphere, heating and cooling rate, microstructure and the pellet density [29]. Depending on the amount of oxygen loss, the ceramic can be insulating, semiconducting, metallic or can be electrically heterogeneous, with different regions corresponding to different conductivities. Partial or complete reoxidation can occur on cooling the sample from its annealing temperature which can lead to gradients in oxygen content and hence Ti^{3+} ions [30]. Losing a small amount of oxygen makes it conducting, but the exact mechanism of electronic conduction whether it is polaronic type [31] or conduction band mechanism type [32] has still been a question of debate. On annealing at a high temperature, oxygen ions diffuse out of the unit cells, leaving behind oxygen vacancies and electrons which can be expressed as

where $V_{\ddot{O}}$ is the oxygen vacancy created. The electron is taken by the Ti^{4+} ion and small amount of it changes to Ti^{3+} . The transfer of electrons from Ti^{4+} to Ti^{3+} brings about conduction in oxygen deficient BTO. On the other hand undoped BTO is an insulator with a band gap of around 3.0 eV.

Few papers have reported the n-type of conductive behaviour in polycrystalline $BaTiO_3$ reduced in vacuum [33] and single crystal $BaTiO_3$ reduced in hydrogen atmosphere [34] through thermoelectric measurements. Eror and Smyth [35] reported p-type conductivity on annealing BTO single crystals between 800°C and 1200°C at high partial pressure of oxygen and n-type conductivity on annealing at low partial pressure of oxygen. Singly ionised Ba vacancies give rise to p-type conductivity and doubly ionised O vacancies give rise to n-type conductivity. Also, n-type conductivity shows stronger temperature dependence than p-type conductivity.

BTO shows positive temperature coefficient of resistivity (PTCR) effect above ferroelectric phase transition and the resistivity increases to several orders of magnitude [36]. PTCR effect mostly arises due to potential barrier formation at the grain boundaries arising from oxygen absorption or cation vacancies like Ba [37, 38]. Weakly reduced BTO shows an anomalous PTCR effect but if the reduction is very strong, the PTCR effect becomes very poor or in some cases may not be observed at all [39].

Dopants (for example rare earth cations in place of Ba^{2+} and Nb^{5+} in place of Ti^{4+}) added to BTO can give rise to either semiconducting behaviour or insulating behaviour depending on whether the charge compensation is electronic and involves ejection of electrons into the crystal structure or ionic which involves generation of cation vacancies respectively. Although which mechanism prevails is still a question of investigation but usually at low dopant concentration the conduction mechanism is electronic and at high dopant concentration, it is ionic [40].

Chapter 3 Objectives

This thesis addresses some of the problems on oxygen deficient BaTiO_3 ($\text{BaTiO}_{3-\delta}$) that have remain unexplored.

Specifically, the main motivation behind this work is to study the following

- 1) Presence of both ferroelectricity and Conductivity in BTO that arises due to completely contrary mechanisms. Ferroelectricity depends on polarised charges which are localised and conduction requires the presence of itinerant electrons.
- 2) Optimizing the annealing conditions to control oxygen deficiency in BTO
- 3) Determining Oxygen deficiency δ in $\text{BaTiO}_{3-\delta}$ through Reitveld Analysis, EDAX (Energy Dispersive Analysis of X-Ray), XPS (X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy), titration, EELS (electron energy loss spectroscopy).
- 4) Studying Dielectric Properties of Pristine BaTiO_3 and Oxygen Deficient $\text{BaTiO}_{3-\delta}$

All the above point have been addressed in chapter 5.

Chapter 4 Experimental Techniques

4.1 Impedance Spectroscopy

Impedance Spectroscopy (IS) is a very useful tool to understand electroceramic materials like dielectrics and ferroelectrics. IS can be used to understand the microstructure, intrinsic behaviour of the material. It can be used to understand the contributions of the bulk region, grain boundary region and electrode sample interface and also quantify the contribution of each region to electrical behaviour of the material.

Electrical properties of a material can be equivalently represented by a model comprising of Resistors and Capacitors which can help us understand and interpret the impedance data better. The bulk components of the material are usually represented by a resistor and a capacitor in parallel (RC circuit). But if the material contains a number of grain boundaries (Can be found out by Spectroscopy studies like SEM and TEM), a parallel RC circuit representing grain boundaries can be added in series to the Grain (bulk) RC circuit. Many a times even a parallel RC circuit representing electrode-sample interface is also added in series to the Grain and Grain boundary RC circuits as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: A model of a material represented in the form of RC circuit has been shown. a) The material is shown in the form of a cube containing grain, grain boundaries and electrode. b) A single grain with a grain boundary has been shown c) Three RC circuits have been connected in series to represent the effect of electrodes, grain boundaries and grains. R_{el} is the resistance of the electrode, C_{el} is the

capacitance of the electrode, R_g is the resistance of the grain, C_g is the capacitance of the grain, R_{gb} is the resistance of the grain boundary and C_{gb} is the capacitance of the grain boundary[41]

IS allows us to take measurements of four quantities at a given time. Rest of the quantities can be derived from these four parameters using relations further given in this chapter. In this thesis we have taken measurements of total impedance ($|Z|$), Real part of complex impedance (R_s), the parallel capacitance (C_p) and the imaginary part of complex impedance given as X .

$$Z^* = Z' + j Z''$$

Where Z^* is the complex form of impedance, Z' or R_s is the real part of complex impedance and Z'' is the imaginary part of complex impedance represented as 'X' in this thesis. All parameters have their value in ohms the total impedance is given as

$$|Z| = (Z'^2 + Z''^2)^{0.5}$$

A simple model of a resistance (R_s) in series with a parallel resistance R_p and Capacitance C_p has been shown in figure 6

Figure 6: A model of a RC circuit. A resistor R_s is connected in series to a parallel RC circuit consisting of a resistor R_p in parallel to Capacitor C

The total impedance is can be calculated as follows

$$\frac{1}{Z_2} = \frac{1}{R_s} + \frac{1}{j\omega C_p}$$

$$Z_2 = \frac{Rp * \frac{1}{j\omega Cp}}{Rp + \frac{1}{j\omega Cp}}$$

$$Z = Z_1 + Z_2$$

Where Z_1 is the impedance of the series component and Z_2 is the impedance of the parallel component of the circuit.

$$Z = R_s + \frac{R_p}{1 + jR_p\omega Cp} * \frac{1 - jR_p\omega Cp}{1 - jR_p\omega Cp}$$

$$Z = R_s + \frac{Rp(1 - jRp\omega Cp)}{1 + (Rp\omega Cp)^2}$$

$$Z = \left(R_s + \frac{Rp}{1 + Rp^2\omega^2 Cp^2} \right) - j \frac{Rp^2\omega^2 Cp^2}{1 + Rp^2\omega^2 Cp^2}$$

$$Z = Z' + jZ''$$

Where the real part of complex impedance (Z') can be written as

$$Z' = \left(R_s + \frac{Rp}{1 + Rp^2\omega^2 Cp^2} \right)$$

And imaginary part Z'' can be written as

$$Z'' = \frac{Rp^2\omega^2 Cp^2}{1 + Rp^2\omega^2 Cp^2}$$

Figure 7: Real part of Complex impedance (Z' or R_s) in ohms dependence on frequency. The circles represent the experimental data and fit represent the fitted curve of the data.

Figure 7 shows the real part of impedance (R_s) versus frequency. As frequency tends to 0, Z' tends to the sum of series resistance and parallel resistance and as frequency tends to infinity, Z'' tends to series resistance. Dependence of Z'' on frequency has been shown in figure 8. The peak of the curve gives the value of the relaxation frequency which has been proved below

$$Z'' = -\frac{Rp^2 \omega Cp}{1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2}$$

$$\frac{dZ''}{d\omega} = \frac{1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2 (-Rp^2 Cp) + Rp^2 \omega Cp * 2\omega Rp^2 Cp^2}{(1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2)^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{dZ''}{d\omega} = \frac{-Rp^2 Cp - Rp^4 \omega^2 Cp^3 + 2\omega^2 Rp^4 Cp^3}{(1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2)^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{dZ''}{d\omega} = \frac{-Rp^2 Cp + \omega^2 Rp^4 Cp^3}{(1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2)^2} = 0$$

$$\omega^2 Rp^4 Cp^3 = Rp^2 Cp$$

$$\omega = \frac{1}{Rp Cp} = \frac{1}{\tau}$$

Where τ is the time constant.

Figure 8: Complex part of impedance (Z'' or X) has been plotted versus frequency. The circles represent the observed data points and fit represents the fitted curve of the experimental data. The peak gives the value of relaxation frequency beyond which the bound charges are no longer able to orient themselves with the fast changing applied ac electric field.

Graph of Z'' versus Z' is called Nyquist plot (shown in figure 9). Nyquist plot gives us a lot of information about the properties of the material. It is very sensitive to changes and it is quite easy to understand as most of the parameters can be directly read from the curve. A semicircle is a representative of a single time constant. But in almost all materials, mostly more than one semicircles are found corresponding to different relaxation mechanisms. The radius of the semicircle is equal to half the value of parallel resistance. The intercept of the semicircle towards higher frequency gives us the value of series resistance and the intercept towards the lower frequency side gives us the value of sum of both series and parallel resistance. Each point in the Nyquist plot also known as the Cole-Cole plot is a representative of a single frequency. Most of the times we do not get complete semicircles, instead only a portion of the semicircle is obtained. The semicircle equation can be derived in the following way

$$Z' = R_s + \frac{Rp}{1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2} \quad Z'' = -\frac{Rp^2 \omega Cp}{1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2}$$

$$\left[Z' - \left(R_s + \frac{Rp}{2} \right) \right]^2 = \left[\frac{Rp}{1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2} - \frac{Rp}{2} \right]^2$$

$$\left[Z' - \left(R_s + \frac{Rp}{2} \right) \right]^2 = \frac{Rp^2}{(1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2)^2} + \frac{Rp^2}{4} - \frac{Rp^2}{(1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2)^2}$$

$$Z''^2 = \frac{Rp^4 \omega^2 Cp^2}{(1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2)^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\left[Z' - \left(Rs + \frac{Rp}{2} \right) \right] \right)^2 + (Z'')^2 \\ &= \frac{Rp^2}{(1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2)^2} + \frac{Rp^4}{(1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2)^2} + \frac{Rp^2}{4} - \frac{Rp^2}{(1 + \omega^2 Rp^2 Cp^2)} \\ &= \left(\frac{Rp}{2} \right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

The above equation represents the equation of a semicircle with centre at $\left(Rs + \frac{Rp}{2} \right)$ and radius of $\frac{Rp}{2}$

Figure 9: Z'' (X) versus Z' (Rs) also known as the Cole-Cole plot has been shown. The curve is a semicircle with each point describing a data at a particular frequency. The arrow shows the direction of increasing frequency. The circles are measured data and fit the curve fit of the experimental value.

We studied some parallel RC circuits with different time constants mentioned in table 1. We calculated the theoretical time constant and the measured time constant by fitting the curves for the cole-cole plot. We can clearly see that as the frequency increases the time difference between theoretical and measured time constant decreases. A graph of time constant versus frequency has been shown in figure 10. The squares represent the theoretical time constant as

calculated from the value of resistors and capacitors taken and the Circles represent the measured time constants as calculated from the value of resistance and capacitance given by the LCR meter.

Frequency (Hz)	Theoretical τ (s)	Measured τ (s)	Error in τ (s)
70 Hz	2.2E-3	2.20E-3	0.07E-3
91 Hz	1.75E-3	1.86E-3	-0.11E-3
508 Hz	3.13E-4	3.19E-4	-0.06E-4
1000 Hz	1.59E-4	1.61E-4	-0.02E-4
96574 Hz	1.65E-6	1.42E-6	0.23E-6
682483 Hz	2.33E-7	2.30E-7	0.33E-7
984005 Hz	1.62E-7	1.62E-7	0.00

Table 1: Various Combinations of Resistors and capacitors have been taken with different time constants or corresponding frequency shown in first coloumn. The theoretical time constant (τ) has been calculated and shown in second coloumn. The experiemental τ has been shown in the third coloumn and difference in theoretical and experiemental time constant has been shown in the last coloumn.

Figure 10: Plot of logarithm of time constant (τ) versus log of frequency (Hz) has been shown. The black squares show the theoretical calculated value of time constant and the red circles show the experimental time constant. The error bars shows the difference between the calculated and measured value.

Impedance Spectroscopy can be used to study the dielectric behaviour of a material. The complex dielectric constant (ϵ^*) is defined as below

$$\epsilon^* = \epsilon' + j \epsilon''$$

where ϵ' is the real part of the permittivity and ϵ'' is the imaginary part of the dielectric constant also known as the dielectric loss. We calculated the dielectric constant from the complex impedance (Z^*) using the following formula

$$\epsilon^* = \frac{1}{j\omega C_0 Z^*}$$

where C_0 is the capacitance without the sample. Hence the dielectric permittivity can be written as

$$\epsilon' = \frac{Z''}{\omega C_0 (Z'^2 + Z''^2)}$$

An the dielectric loss (Z'') can be written as

$$\epsilon'' = \frac{Z'}{\omega C_0 (Z'^2 + Z''^2)}$$

We can calculate the dielectric loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) defined as

$$\tan \delta = \frac{\epsilon''}{\epsilon'}$$

Using the dielectric parameters values, we can calculate the ac conductivity (σ_{ac}) defined as

$$\sigma_{ac} = \epsilon'' * \omega * \epsilon_0$$

where ϵ_0 is the dielectric permittivity of vacuum. Its value is 8.85×10^{-12} F/m

We have defined the impedance and dielectric relations for a simple RC circuit. But usually most materials are heterogeneous and have more than one relaxation mechanism and have various contributions to dielectric data coming from different sources like the grain boundaries and grains. In that scenario we see two arcs in the complex impedance rather than one. The higher frequency arc represents the grain or the bulk effect and the lower frequency arc represent the grain boundary effect. In many cases, only a single arc will be observed if the resistance of the grain boundary dominates the grain resistance i.e. $R_{gb} \gg R_g$. In the Z'' versus frequency plot, we get two peaks corresponding to two relaxations of the grain boundaries and the grains. The higher frequency peak describes the relaxation of the bulk and the lower frequency peak describes the behaviour of the grain boundary. The capacitance of the grain boundary is also much higher than the capacitance of the grain since the thickness of the grain boundary is much smaller than the size of the grain.

4.2 Temperature dependent Impedance Spectroscopy

To study the temperature dependent impedance behaviour of BTO, we have used Closed Cycle Refrigerator (CCR) that can cool samples down to 10K. The whole system consist of Lakeshore temperature controller, Rotary pump, Vacuum jacket, Radiation shield, Compressor and cryogen safe pipelines (shown in figure 11). A variety of electrical experiments can be done with temperature ranging from 10K to 415K. CCR uses Helium gas which is compressed cooled and then expanded. On expanding it takes away the heat from the sample mounting stage and returns back to the compressor where it is again compressed and cooled. CCR is safer and very easy to handle since it does not use liquid cryogens like Nitrogen or Helium. The only disadvantage is that it consumes a lot of power.

Figure 11: Temperature dependent Impedance spectroscopy set-up. 10K CCR, Compressor, gas lines and rotary pump have been shown in the figure

A schematic of the CCR has been shown in figure 12 explaining the working of each part of the CCR. Helium gas goes from the compressor to the expander through one of the gas lines and comes back from the other. He-3 is used to cool down the temperature to 10K as it can remain in liquefied state almost till absolute 0 due to weak Vander Waal's forces. This CCR does not require filling Helium again. Oil based Vacuum pump is used to remove unwanted gases and particles. It reduces pressure inside the apparatus which causes the gases to vaporize. Vacuum helps in creating a pressure gradient so that flow of cryogen can be controlled. Usually $10E-5$ mbar is enough to start the compressor. The sample mounting stage is covered by a radiation shield which protects it from the thermal radiation given by the Vacuum Shroud. The radiation shield is covered by a Vacuum jacket which reduces the heat load on the expander caused by the conduction and convection from the instrumentation skirt.

Figure 12: Schematic of the inside of a Closed Cycle refrigerator (CCR)

Chapter 5 Results

5.1 Sample preparation of BaTiO₃ pellet

We have taken 0.2g of BaTiO₃ powder to make our pellets. Density of BaTiO₃ is 6.02 g/ cm³ and the radius of the pellets were 1cm in diameter which implies that the thickness of the pellet was small approximately around 0.3 mm. Such small thickness not only helps in forming homogenous pellet in the die with lesser density variation but also helps in reducing the coercive strength of the material. The smaller thickness also helps in diffusing out oxygen from the bulk and the surface which can decrease the resistance of the material.

We have used polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as binder. PVA is water soluble, has great binding strength, undergoes a glass transition around 85°C and boils off around 200°C to 300°C. We used 1% PVA dissolved in water because higher the water content the glass transition temperature of PVA decreases and helps in binding the particles in the compact strongly. Binder was mixed with BaTiO₃ powder and crushed and grounded in a mortar and pestle to form homogenous agglomerates.

We used hydraulic press to provide the pressure and a uniaxial die to form the pellet. We applied a pressure of 60 kN/mm², the effective pressure on the powder is less because of the friction present between the walls. We used paraffin oil as a lubricant to reduce the friction and to form homogenous pellet with lesser density variation. The boiling point of the paraffin oil is around 300°C, which is lower than the temperature at which the pellet is sintered.

After forming the green compact, we again crushed the pellet and ground the powder. The step was repeated so as to decrease the density variation and increase the homogeneity of the material.

Finally, we sintered the pellet in the furnace in air at a temperature of 600°C and maintained the temperature for 2 hours. At such high temperature, the binder, lubricants, organic and volatile impurities boil off leading to the formation of a dense pellet with greater strength. Sintering helps in fusion and compaction of the particles by reducing the surface area and hence the surface energy. The melting point of BaTiO₃ is around 1600°C so sintering should be done at a lower temperature because too high temperature and longer sintering time can lead to undesirable grain growth.

5.2 Sample preparation of oxygen deficient BaTiO₃ powder and pellet

The major motivation of our thesis is to understand the characteristics, dielectric and transport properties of oxygen deficient BaTiO₃. In many papers it has been reported that heating the ceramic oxide in air or vacuum causes the material to become oxygen deficient [42-43].

Vacuum annealing creates oxygen vacancy and helps in removal of chemisorbed oxygen from the surface and grain boundary [43]. Annealing at a higher temperature activates diffusion process of oxygen and desorption of oxygen from the grains and grain boundaries respectively. We annealed the pristine BaTiO₃ powder and the pristine BaTiO₃ pellet in vacuum at temperature of 800°C and 900°C for 3 hours. But the annealed pellet/powder did not show a change in colour or appeared darker. When compared to the X-ray diffraction (XRD) data of the pristine BaTiO₃ sample, the oxygen deficient sample showed no change in peaks or peak positions or the occupancy of the ions in the unit cell calculated through Reitveld Refinement (Figure 13).

Figure 13: XRD data of pristine BTO and vacuum annealed BTO at 800°C and 900°C. The inset shows the peak (111). We clearly see that there is no peak shift between pristine and oxygen deficient BTO data.

Therefore, we next tried annealing the pristine sample in reducing atmosphere of 95% Ar and 5% H₂ in a tube at temperature of 900°C and 1000°C for 3 hours. Since H₂ is a combustible gas, Ar is added for stability. We further studied the XRD of the oxygen deficient sample and compared it with BaTiO₃ pristine pellet (figure 14). We find that there is a peak shift towards higher angle in oxygen deficient sample. According to Bragg's law (equation 4), increase in angular peak position implies a decrease in the interplanar distance *d*, therefore we can say that there are structural changes in the lattice and the lattice constant decreases. The decrease in lattice constants can be due to oxygen vacancies created [44] or it can be due to barium vacancy or A-site defect in the lattice [45]. The details of XRD study along with Reitveld refinement have been mentioned in section

Figure 14: XRD data for pristine BTO and oxygen deficient BTO annealed at temperatures of 900°C and 1000°C in Ar/H₂ atmosphere. The inset shows the (111) peak. There is clearly a marked shift in the peak position of pristine and oxygen deficient sample.

5.3 X-ray diffraction and Rietveld Refinement of pristine and oxygen deficient BaTiO₃

We studied the X-ray diffraction (XRD) of pristine and oxygen deficient BaTiO₃ (annealed at 900°C) pellet using a Rigaku Miniflex2 diffractometer. It uses a monochromatic X-ray source of wavelength 1.54 Å from a Cu source operating at 30 kV and 15 mA. The data was collected in theta/2 theta scanning mode ranging from 10° to 80° at intervals of 0.02°. The Rietveld Refinement was carried out using Fullprof Software [25]. This program allows us to keep any number of parameters constant and any number of parameters can be refined simultaneously. We can also introduce constraints between parameters [46]. The background points were calculated from the WinPlotr program using automatic background selection of points. The initial model for our XRD experimental data was taken from Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD). For refinement, Pseudo-Voigt peak shape was selected and linear interpolation method was used for background correction. Debye-Scherrer was used as diffraction geometry and least squares method was used as a refinement weighting model. Tetragonal phase with P4mm space group was given as input. Refining a number of parameters at a given time can crash the program, therefore only a few uncorrelated, stable parameters should be refined at first. We first refined the overall Scale factor, then corrected for the zero shift and the background points. The lattice parameters were refined next followed by the overall Debye-Waller factor or the B-factor. The peak shape parameters (U, V, W, IG, Eta_0 and X) including the asymmetry parameters were refined. Asymmetry in peaks can be a sign of 2 peaks or future peak splitting. These parameters also correct the shift of peaks to lower angles caused by finite size of the sample and finite slit heights [47-48]. Plate like crystallites have a tendency to align themselves along the axis of sample holder and these intrinsic anomalies can be corrected using preferred orientation parameters. Isotropic thermal factors were refined next individually, their values are highly unstable and correlated with the occupancy factor [49], therefore they should be refined separately. We then refined the occupancy of each atom separately followed by correction of the instrumental displacement factor. Scattering intensity depends on the number of electrons an ion has, and since oxygen is a small atom, its occupancy was kept fixed during the refining process. Occupancies were calculated according to equation 15. During refining it was made sure that all parameters have physical values after refinement. Many a times, there are chances of falling into a local minimum of any of the parameters meaning that our model will keep on trying to match the experimental data even by setting nonphysical values to the parameters.

All the observations have been mentioned in tables 2, 3 and 4. The XRD experimental data of pristine BTO and oxygen deficient BTO along with the fit values obtained through Rietveld method and the residues (difference between observed intensity and measured intensity) has been shown in figure 15 and figure 16 respectively. The agreement factors for both pristine and oxygen deficient BTO has been mentioned in table 3

Figure 15: XRD data for Pristine BTO. The black lines are the experimental values (experimental data) and the red lines are obtained through profile fit in Rietveld refinement (calculated data). The residue is the difference between the experimental and calculated values

Figure 16: XRD data for Oxygen deficient BTO annealed at 900°C. The black lines are the experimental values (experimental data) and the red lines are obtained through profile fit in Rietveld refinement (calculated data). The residue is the difference between the experimental and calculated values

From figure 14, we can see that the peaks shift towards higher angles and the lattice parameters decrease for oxygen deficient BTO. This can occur due to removal of oxygen ions from the unit cell which can cause the volume of the cell to decrease. The calculated lattice parameters are very close to experimental values [50]. Since the tetragonal ratio remains the same, we can assume that in plane oxygen ions diffuse out during annealing. The overall B-factor and isotropic thermal factor were all positive implying the stability of our model. B-factors are very sensitive and their values being negative implies that the model is not correct. Since we studied the sample at room temperature the overall B-factor was very small. The full width at half maxima (FWHM) of oxygen deficient BTO was more than that of pristine BTO. Since crystallite size (calculated from Scherrer's formula mentioned in equation 14) is inversely proportional to FWHM, it implies that crystallite size of oxygen deficient BTO is

less than that of Pristine. This again supported our assertion that oxygen loss can cause the decrease in size of crystals. The decrease in crystallite size can also be due to high sintering and annealing temperature which causes the grains to fuse together thereby lessening the number of grain boundaries. We calculated FWHM and crystallite size of (111) peak because it is the only peak in the tetragonal phase that does not undergo broadening due to line splitting and in the absence of any lattice strain, they contribute only to the crystallite size effect. We also calculated the occupancy of each atom given by equation 15 in chapter 2. Since oxygen atoms almost remain invisible to the X-rays, we kept their occupancies fixed at 0.125 and 0.25 for c-axis parallel oxygen ion and a,b axis parallel oxygen ions respectively. The barium occupancy decreased for the oxygen deficient sample implying that there were some Ba loss due to annealing at high temperatures. We also saw an increase in the occupancy of Ti ion. Although there was no source or drain of Ti ions, the increase in its value in the oxygen deficient sample can be possible due to addition of extra electrons. It is well known that the electrons given by the oxygen ion is taken by the 3d conduction band orbitals of Ti^{4+} ions. A small number of Ti^{4+} gets converted to Ti^{3+} . The continuous transfer of electrons from Ti^{3+} to Ti^{4+} is responsible for conduction in oxygen deficient BTO.

	a = b (Å)	c (Å)	Tetragonal ratio (c/a)
Pristine BTO	4.00	4.03	1.01
Oxygen deficient BTO	3.98	4.01	1.01
BTO (literature) [50]	3.99	4.03	1.01

Table 2 : Lattice parameters of oxygen deficient BTO and pristine BTO. Lattice constants as given in literature have also been mentioned.

	FWHM (deg)	Peak Position (deg) 2θ	Crystallite size D (nm)
Pristine BTO	0.2699	38.94	32.62
Oxygen deficient BTO	0.3408	39.22	25.86

Table 3 : Full width at half maxima for peak (111) is mentioned in degrees for both Pristine and oxygen deficient BTO. The position of (111) peak in degree is given. The crystallite size has been calculated from the Scherrer's formula.

Ions	Pristine BTO		Oxygen deficient BTO	
	Isotropic B-factor (\AA^2)	Occupancy	Isotropic B-factor (\AA^2)	Occupancy
Ba	0.01922	0.12471	0.47672	0.12406
Ti	0.45942	0.12168	0.60360	0.12949
O1	1.58538	0.12500	1.76707	0.12500
O2	0.19636	0.25000	1.19196	0.25000

Table 4: Isotropic B-factor or temperature factor and occupancy have been mentioned for Pristine BTO and oxygen deficient BTO for all ions. O1 is the oxygen parallel to the c-axis and O2 are the planar oxygen ions

All the agreement factor values have been mentioned in table 5. The Chi-square values are close to 1.

	Pristine BTO	Oxygen deficient BTO
R_{wp}	25.20	25.90
R_p	24.30	32.5
R_{exp}	15.31	18.41
R_B	5.14	5.12
χ^2	2.71	1.98

Table 2: Agreement factors for Pristine and Oxygen deficient BTO.

5.4 Temperature dependent Impedance Spectroscopy

To understand the electronic, dielectric properties of our material we studied the temperature dependent impedance spectroscopy in temperature range from 10K to 415K. Through impedance spectroscopy we can measure very high resistances of megaohm range along with capacitance. Since our material was dielectric and of high resistance, IS was a good choice for studying the electrical properties. Most of the previous studies on BTO were done at high temperatures only. But besides high temperature, we also studied the low temperature effect on the oxygen deficient sample annealed at 900°C. Different polarization mechanisms are associated with different thermally activated processes, studying the low temperature

behaviour can help us understand the origin of all the polarization mechanisms. All the measurements were taken using the four probe technique as shown in figure 17. Four probe technique removes the contact resistance contribution. The impedance data was taken from Hioki 3532-50 LCR Hitester in the frequency range from 50 Hz to 1E6 Hz. The BNC cables were used since they can easily operate at higher frequencies efficiently. Temperature studies were done using 10K CCR (HC -4A Sumitomo Cryogenics Zephyr) connected to Lake shore (335) temperature controller and HiCube Vacuum pump. The sample was attached to the mounting stage in CCR using Teflon, mica sheet and cryogenic high vacuum grease (Apiezon N). All of them were thermally conducting and electrically insulating.

Figure 17: Four Probe technique used to study the impedance behaviour. The diameter of the pellet is 1 cm. The distance between the electrical contacts is 120 micron. The contacts are of length 1mm x 1mm and the thickness of the metallic contacts on the pellet is 5mm. Current (I) flows through the outer contacts and voltage difference (V) is measured through the inner contacts.

5.4.1 Contact Optimization for BaTiO₃ pellet

In order to study the electronic and dielectric behaviour of BTO, we tried to optimize the best metallic contact for our ceramic. We studied four metallic contacts, Copper/Gold (Cu/Au), Chromium/Gold (Cr/Ag), Silver paste (Ag) and Silver/Aluminium (Ag/Al). These metals were deposited on the pellet in a deposition chamber as shown in figure 17. From figure 18, we can see that both Cr/Au and Cu/Au gave lower resistances as compared to the other

metallic contacts. But the Z'' or X (imaginary part of complex impedance) peak for pristine BTO was shifted towards the lower frequency side and therefore not visible. Since we wanted to study the relaxation mechanism and find the relaxation frequency, we chose Cr/Au as electrical contacts for our pellets. Pristine BTO with Cr/Au contact has both lower resistance and visible relaxation peak.

Figure 18: Complex Impedance study of pristine BTO with different metallic Contacts at room temperature. We took Ag paste, Cr/Au, Cu/Au and Ag/Al as metallic contacts.

5.4.2 Dielectric Study of oxygen deficient BTO annealed at 900°C

We studied the temperature dependent dielectric behaviour of oxygen deficient BTO annealed at 900°C using the four probe technique with Cr/Au as metallic contacts (shown in figure 17) from 10K to 415K.

The real part of complex impedance versus frequency has been drawn in figure 19. The lower frequency region (||) represents the contribution of the grain boundaries. The middle region shown by || gives the value of bulk resistance. We can clearly see that as the temperature increases the bulk resistance decreases from 10K to 50K to 100K finally becoming vanishingly small as the temperature is increased further. This is because as the temperature increases the dipoles in the bulk become more thermally active, thus lowering the value of the resistance. At very high frequencies (|||), the Z' falls sharply because at such high frequencies,

all polarization, mobility mechanisms fail to follow the rapidly changing direction of the applied ac electric field.

Figure 19: The real part of complex impedance (Z') versus frequency at temperature of 10K, 50K, 100K and 300K. Three different regions of the curve have been marked in the graph shown by (I) in the lower frequency region, (II) in the middle region and (III) at higher frequency region.

Figure 20: Nyquist plot for BTO sample drawn for temperatures 10K, 150K, 200K. The arrow marks the direction of increasing frequency. Z'' is the imaginary part of complex impedance and Z' is the real part

From figure 20 we can clearly see that there are two relaxation processes one related to the relaxation of grain boundaries and other to the relaxations of grains. The semicircular arc at high frequency end is a clear indication of the presence of bound charges like the dipoles in the grains. The semicircle at the higher frequency end is mainly attributed to the grains and the end towards lower frequency mainly attributed to the grain boundaries. This is because at lower frequencies, the mobile charges accumulate at the grain boundaries and stay there for a long period of time before reversing their direction to the opposite side on changing the direction of ac electric field. At higher frequencies, the mobile charges do not get enough time to reach the grain boundary and hence at higher frequencies only bound charges or dipoles of the grain boundaries and the grains contribute [51]. Also, the lower end shows a very high value of resistance and capacitance. This is because when the frequency of the applied electric field is low, the free charges accumulate at the grain- grain boundary surface and since the thickness of the grain boundary is very small, it leads to overall high capacitance. The grains are smaller in size than the grain boundaries; therefore they show low

capacitive behaviour. With temperature increase we can see that the resistance and capacitance of the grain boundary increases as more charges accumulate at the grain boundary region due to thermal motion. The resistance of the grains decrease with increasing temperature because the dipoles get more thermally active and is able to respond well to the changing electric field. The free charge carriers, defects, disorders, electrons and ions mainly contribute to the resistance and capacitance of grain boundary region. As our samples were oxygen deficient, oxygen vacancies could have been created at the grain boundaries leading to an increase in the resistivity of the grain boundaries.

Figure 21: Dielectric loss tangent versus frequency shown at different temperatures given in Kelvin.

Dielectric loss tangent (ratio of imaginary part of dielectric permittivity and real part of dielectric permittivity) versus frequency has been plotted in figure 21. Dielectric constant is the loss of energy in the material and occurs because the polarization lags behind the applied electric field mainly caused by the grain boundaries [52]. We can clearly see that as the frequency increases the dielectric loss decreases at all temperatures. This is because at lower frequencies more types of polarization occur like ionic, orientational, electronic, dipolar, interfacial but as the frequency increases, the molecules are not able to reorient quickly to the fast changing field and hence they relaxes leading to a decrease in the dielectric loss value. This kind of behaviour is very typical of every dielectric material. Higher value at low

frequencies can be due to increased resistivity of the grain boundaries as compared to the grains [52] Dielectric loss mainly arises due to impurities, imperfections and defects in the crystal structure. Materials that contain a large number of pores have low dielectric constant and high dielectric loss.

Conductivity in a material arises due to electric conduction of mobile charges and weakly bound charges on the application of an external electric field and is a characteristic of dielectric loss in the medium. It mostly depends on the size of the grains and their distributions, impurities present and its structural symmetry. Ac conductivity dependence on frequency follows a simple power law behaviour given by A.K Jonscher [53] shown in equation 24

$$\sigma_{ac} = \sigma_o + A\omega^s \quad (24)$$

Where σ_{ac} is the ac conductivity , σ_o is the frequency independent quantity and is usually related to the dc conductivity of the sample, s is an exponent that takes the value from 0 to 1 and A is a temperature dependent quantity. Value of s less than 1 implies hopping mechanism of charge carriers with translational motion. Ac conductivity dependence on frequency has been shown in figure 22. We mentioned earlier that at low frequencies since there are large number of carriers present, the overall conductivity of the sample decreases, since these carriers act as barriers to the passing current. But as the frequency keeps on increasing the conductivity also increases because of the relaxation of mobile charge carriers and release of space charges.

Figure 22: Ac conductance versus frequency shown at different temperatures

Next we studied the Capacitance (C_p) versus frequency curve of BTO which gave us very different values as measured from the 10K CCR apparatus and another high temperature set-up (shown in figure 23). The capacitance value of 10K CCR was of the order ranging from 10^{-8} to 10^{-10} F. But the capacitance value from the high temperature set-up was of the order of 10^{-11} F. This made us conclude that besides the capacitance of the material, we have some additional capacitance coming from the 10K CCR temperature dependent IS set-up.

Figure 23: Capacitance (C_p) versus frequency of oxygen deficient BTO has been shown. a,b) The measurement was taken from the 10K CCR ranging from 10K to 415K. c) The measurement was taken from the high temperature set-up ranging from 70°C to 150°C

Chapter 6 Conclusion

In summary, we studied the Pristine BaTiO₃ and oxygen deficient BaTiO₃. We tried to make oxygen deficient BTO by annealing in Vacuum at 800°C and 900°C and by annealing in reducing atmosphere of Ar/H₂ at 900°C and 1000°C. We indeed proved that the vacuum treated pellet was not oxygen deficient. The Ar/H₂ treated pellet was oxygen deficient which was proved through Rietveld Technique and XRD analysis. Also, the Ar/H₂ treated pellet appeared darker. We did the characterization of our sample through X-ray diffraction and Rietveld Refinement and calculated various results such as the crystallite size, lattice parameters and occupancy. We studied Impedance Spectroscopy (IS) and modelled the dielectric behaviour of a parallel RC circuit. We studied the working of a 10K CCR temperature set-up. We optimized the metallic contact for pristine BTO pellet and found out that the most efficient contact would be Cr/Au out of Cu/Au, Ag paste and Ag/Al. We also studied the dielectric behaviour of oxygen deficient BTO annealed at 900°C and studied its Complex impedance, resistance, capacitance, dielectric loss and ac conductivity.

In future, we intend to take the dielectric measurements through lock-in amplifier which would nullify the extra contribution to capacitance coming from the experimental set-up. We would take EDAX measurement to determine the elemental composition. We would also like to take the SEM of our data to validate our assertion of formation of grain boundaries that gives a major contribution to the Impedance data. At the end we would like to study the Metal-Insulator transition in oxygen deficient BTO.

Since years numerous studies conducted on both doped and undoped BTO as films, single crystals, polycrystals have shown that it has numerous industrial applications owing to its interesting physics. Our work on pristine and oxygen deficient BTO will help us to understand more about the temperature (both low and high) and doping effect on the properties of BTO.

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